

DETERMINATION OF DEFORMATIONS BY PHOTOGRAMMETRIC METHOD

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Abstract

In the article, subsidence and deformations are investigated by the photogrammetric method during the periods of deformation. Here, the in-plane photogrammetric method and stereophotogrammetric methods in any direction are compared for determining deformations.

Keywords: photograph, deformation, characterization elements, stereo pair, photogrammetric method

Determining the collapse and deformations of the device by photogrammetric method has a number of advantages over other methods. These advantages include: the objectivity of the obtained results, the ability to measure objects of large area at the same time, the ability to determine the positions of any number of points, relative simplicity and high measurement accuracy. Compared to other methods, the photogrammetric method allows determining the displacement of points in a three-dimensional coordinate system at the same time.

The essence of the determination of subsidence and deformations by photogrammetric method consists in calculating the differences of the measured coordinates of the installation points based on the photographs taken during the zero and deformation periods.

$$\Delta X = (Y/f)(x_k - x_m) = M\Delta x_{m,k}; \quad \Delta Z = (Z/f)(z_k - z_m) = M\Delta z_{m,k}. \quad (1)$$

If the images from periods m and k are processed together, the values of the quantities $\Delta x_{m,k}$ and $\Delta z_{m,k}$ can be determined without direct measurement. For example, an image of period m is placed on the left cassette of a stereo instrument, and an image of period k is placed on the right cassette. At this time, a stereo effect is detected for the points that receive a displacement, and based on these images, the $\Delta x_{m,k}$ and $\Delta z_{m,k}$ displacements will be equal to the longitudinal and q transverse parallaxes, respectively.

By stereophotogrammetric method, photographing of the object is carried out from two points - a base of length B , as a result, stereopair images are obtained. In periods m and k , coordinates $\Delta x_{m,k}$ and $\Delta z_{m,k}$ and longitudinal parallax p_m, p_k are measured based on images taken from the same base. The deformation along the three coordinate axes is calculated by the following formula:

$$\Delta X = B \left(\frac{x_k}{p_k} - \frac{x_m}{p_m} \right); \quad \Delta Z = B \left(\frac{z_k}{p_k} - \frac{z_m}{p_m} \right);$$

$$\Delta Y = Bf \left(\frac{1}{p_k} - \frac{1}{p_m} \right). \quad (2)$$

When the deformation is determined by the stereophotogrammetric method, the photos in the periods m

Depending on the given task, two methods are used: the plane photogrammetric method (zero base method) and the stereophotogrammetric method for determining deformations in any direction.

In the photogrammetric method, deformation is determined in the XZ plane, which is parallel to the plane of the photograph. In order to keep the elements of orientation from the same point all the time, photography is done in a fixed position of the camera. Based on the coordinates of points m and k in different periods measured from the image, the distance Y measured from the camera to the object in nature, and the known focal distance f of the camera, the deformations ΔX (side shift) and ΔZ (collapse) are determined by the following formula:

and k are measured from the pictures taken by photography from the left side of the base. x_{left}, z_{left} coordinates, values of $\Delta x_{left}, \Delta z_{left}$ displacements are found as in the photogrammetric method. Then the photos taken from the right end of the base are measured in periods m and k , x_{right}, z_{right} coordinates, $\Delta x_{right}, \Delta z_{right}$ displacement values are determined. Measuring z_{right} and Δz_{right} values increases the accuracy of settling determination. In this case, the deformation is calculated by the following formula:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta X &= B \frac{x_{sol} \Delta x_{sa\check{g}} - x_{sa\check{g}} \Delta x_{sol}}{(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})^2 + (x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})}; \\ \Delta Z_{sol} &= B \frac{(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}}) \Delta z_{sol} - z_{sol} (\Delta x_{sol} - \Delta x_{sa\check{g}})}{(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})^2 + (x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})}; \\ \Delta Z_{sa\check{g}} &= B \frac{(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}}) \Delta z_{sa\check{g}} - z_{sa\check{g}} (\Delta x_{sol} - \Delta x_{sa\check{g}})}{(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})^2 + (x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})}; \\ \Delta Z_{orta} &= (\Delta Z_{sol} - \Delta Z_{sa\check{g}})/2; \\ \Delta Y &= -Bf \frac{\Delta x_{sol} - \Delta x_{sa\check{g}}}{(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})^2 + (x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})(x_{sol} - x_{sa\check{g}})}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Formulas (2) - (3) are used when the optical axis of the camera is perpendicular to the base and horizontal from both ends of the base.

By the formula (1), the deformation coordinate is calculated in the planar rectangular coordinate system, whose coordinate origin is at the intersection of the x and z axes of the image. The deformation is expressed in the spatial photogrammetric rectangular coordinate system by formulas (2) and (3). The front focal point of the camera lens set at the left end of the base is taken as the coordinate origin, and the optical axis of the camera is taken as the y -axis.

In order to determine spatial rectangular coordinates and deformations of points on the object based on photographs, it is necessary to know the positions of photographs and stereo pairs at the time of shooting. With the photogrammetric method, the condition of the photograph is determined by nine main parameters - three internal and six external aspect elements. The internal aspect elements determine the position of the center of projection (the rear focal point of the lens) relative to the photograph. They include the f focal length of the camera and the x_0, y_0 coordinates of the head of the photograph. Exterior aspect elements determine the position of the photo in the accepted spatial rectangular

coordinate system. The linear elements of the external aspect are the X_s, Y_s, Z_s coordinates of the projection center determined in the spatial photogrammetric or conventional geodetic coordinate system. The angular elements of the external aspect can be different depending on the adopted coordinate system.

The result. As a result of inevitable errors in the determination and construction of internal and external faceting elements, there is a need to include appropriate corrections in the measured values of coordinates and displacement. Corrections to errors affecting aspect elements include measurements at checkpoints, inspection directions, etc. is mainly given.

Literature

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